

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

¹ Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova

² Shakhnoza Irkinovna Seralieva

¹ Associate Professor of Tashkent State Transport University

ORCID identifier: 0000-0002-6535-0197

² Associate Professor of Tashkent State Transport University

Shaxa2108@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7556260>

Abstract: this article contains information and recommendations about innovative methods of teaching English in general secondary schools and the importance of foreign languages in the education system. The article contains thoughts on the development of attention to foreign languages in our country.

Key words: foreign language, school, innovation, method, method, educational system, professional education, technology, vocabulary, skill.

Today, the ability to know foreign languages is becoming one of the integral parts of professional education. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, there is a high demand for them to learn the language. The ability to use information technologies and modern teaching methods helps to quickly understand new materials. By combining different methods, the teacher is able to solve specific educational programs. In this regard, teachers should familiarize themselves with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, the ability to choose the most effective methods to achieve one's goals is formed. The use of several methods of teaching and learning will give effective results. Teaching is carried out in small steps and is based on the student's existing knowledge system. As time progresses, innovations in every field are increasing. Different styles are also emerging in language teaching. A step-by-step approach to teaching English based on the learner's potential, level, and age gives good results. In this case, students are divided into groups based on teaching at the primary level, teaching at the middle level, and teaching at the higher level. A special program is developed by the teacher for each stage.

At the initial stage, important attention is paid to pronunciation. According to Harmer, the first requirement of native speakers during the conversation is pronunciation. At the beginning of the learning process, the teacher should focus on the student's pronunciation. Grammar and vocabulary are important, but if the speaker's pronunciation is wrong, it's all worthless. Native speakers can understand speech even with grammatical errors if the speaker pronounces the words correctly. Therefore, in teaching, the main focus is on pronunciation. In this

case, using different audios of native speakers gives good results. The teacher should teach the correct pronunciation of letters and words during the lesson. At the initial stage, great attention is paid to the development of oral speech and reading techniques. If we consider the types of speech activities of teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to perform the following tasks when teaching them:

- ❖ *Creating a reading mechanism;*
- ❖ *Developing oral reading techniques;*
- ❖ *Teaching to understand what he has read.*

In addition, students at the elementary level The Present indefinite Tense., The Past indefinite Tense. It is required that they know the tenses of the verbs such as The Future indefinite Tense and be able to clearly use the verb forms in these tenses. Students learn to use singular and plural nouns, to add suffixes "s" or "es" to the third person singular form of verbs in the present indefinite tense, to learn interrogative, negative and command forms of sentences at the initial stage. they acquire during their studies.

Language teaching programs on computers and phones are also a good help for language teaching at the primary and secondary levels. Talk (English speaking practice), Daily English, Learn English (English master), How to speak real English are examples. These programs are structured in such a way that they include reading, listening, and test sections.

Another good way to practice is to record the new words you have learned and listen to them in your spare time. In addition, showing more movies and cartoons with subtitles in English is also an effective way to teach the language. Preparation of additional text topics using the press, periodicals, mass media, internet materials can be given as homework. Students will be interested in texts about interesting research and scientific discoveries.

In conclusion, it should be said that teaching a modern language is aimed at forming a more cultured person, who has the skills of self-analysis and systematization of new knowledge. Innovative methods are an integral part of the modernization of the entire system. This ensures that teachers can familiarize themselves with the most advanced approaches and then integrate them and use them in their work to achieve significant growth in the education system. Many organizations are moving to a new level by using multimedia capabilities to send and receive information. The use of computers and other devices determines the success of the entire educational process.

Sufficient attention should be paid to the formation of speech skills and the development of social flexibility in the trainings conducted during the educational

process. In addition, the success of each lesson in education largely depends on the correct organization of the training. The lesson should be based on the creative cooperation of the teacher and the student. Only then will students be able to think independently and will be educated.

References:

1. Kharatova, S. (2022, November). The role of integrated education in teaching foreign languages. In *Международная конференция академических наук* (Vol. 1, No. 31, pp. 4-6).
2. Kharatova, S., & Khusanova, I. (2022). PROBLEMS OF PLANNING ENGLISH LESSONS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 1(6), 214-217.
3. Kharatova, S. (2022). PERSONAL QUALITIES AND JOBS. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 1(5), 51-55.
4. Kharatova, S. (2022). Modern methods in english language teaching. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 1(6), 31-34.
5. Kharatova, S. (2022). Methods of independent learning english. Best english learning technique. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 1(16), 49-52.
6. Kharatova, S. K. (2022). Concept of Language and Speech. *European journal of innovation in nonformal education*, 2(4), 115-117.
7. Ахматова, Х. Ш. (2017). Концептуальные основы разработки технологий воспитания средствами иностранного языка в техническом вузе. *Современные инновации*, (3 (17)), 41-42.
8. Kharatova, S. (2022, November). The role of integrated education in teaching foreign languages. In *Международная конференция академических наук* (Vol. 1, No. 31, pp. 4-6).
9. Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.
10. Харатова, Ш. Х., & Садикова, М. Б. (2020). Эффективные способы изучения английского языка. *Academy*, (2 (53)), 33-35.
11. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). Tendencies of development of distance education in global transformation. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(10), 353-362.
12. Kharatova, S. (2022). The role of higher education institutions in the development of innovative projects and technologies. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(10), 128-130.
13. Kharatova, S. K. Goals And Tasks Of English Language Teaching. *International Bulletin Of Engineering And Technology*, 2(9).

14. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). Teach english for spesific purposes. *Theoretical and applied science*, 11, 30.
15. Kharatova, s. (2022). Technologies for the development of language skills in english classes. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 1(6), 20-24.
16. Kharatova, S. (2022). methods of independent learning english. best english learning technique. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 1(16), 49-52.
17. Kharatova, S. K. (2022). Concept of Language and Speech. *European journal of innovation in nonformal education*, 2(4), 115-117.
18. Kharatova, S. K. (2022). Communicative exercises in teaching grammar characteristics of english verbs. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(2), 50-53.
19. Kharatova, S. K. (2022). Characteristics of the pedagogical process system. *Science and Education*, 3(6), 681-686.
20. Kharatova, S. (2021). Innovative methods of teaching english. *Экономика и социум*, (3-1), 132-134.
21. Alidjanovna, T. M., Khakimovna, K. S., Tulaboevna, T. G., Shukurovna, A. K., & Xafizovich, U. K. (2021). Lingu-Didactical Basis of Teaching English Learning Vocabulary to the First-Year Uzbek Audience Students. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 415-429.
22. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). Strategic issues of improving spiritual and educational activities in the republic of uzbekistan. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(11), 313-320.
23. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). Problems of foreign language teaching and its solution. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, (4-8), 60-62.
24. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). The importance of foreign language teaching in higher education institutions. *Science and Education*, 2(5), 751-756.
25. Allanazarova, M., Tashtemirova, M., Xaratova, S., Sadiqova, M., & Jalilova, M. (2020). Verbalization of concept “water and fire” in English linguoculturology. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(2), 382-386.
26. Харатова, Ш. Х. (2019). Инновационно–ориентированное развитие как фактор совершенствования опережающего управления вуза на современном этапе. In *Университетский комплекс как региональный центр образования, науки и культуры* (pp. 4117-4120).